

How do lipid nanocarriers – cubosomes affect electrochemical properties of DMPC bilayers deposited on gold (111) electrodes?

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Abstract

Cubosome nanocarriers are promising biomimetic drug delivery systems used in particular for highly toxic drugs in cases where decreasing unwanted side effects is especially important. The properties of electrode supported lipid bilayer prepared by the combined Langmuir-Blodgett and Langmuir-Schaefer techniques were studied using electrochemical techniques following exposure of the film – covered electrode to a solution containing phytantriol - based cubosomes. The inclusion of the carrier in the model membrane under different experimental conditions was probed and the modifications induced in the lipid organization were for the first time inferred by quantitative analysis of the responses of cyclic voltammetry (CV), AC voltammetry and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) as well as blocking assays using a redox probe in the solution. Exposure of a preformed DMPC bilayer to cubosome solution resulted in the improved barrier properties of the film reflecting disintegration of cubosomes and formation of additional phytantriol/ Pluronic F-108 polymer layer on the top of the DMPC bilayer. On the other hand, formation of the layer in the presence of cubosomes in the subphase lead to an increased capacitance of the film since penetration of the lipid layers by the cubosomal phytantriol increased the porosity of the film.

Key-words: 1,2-dimyristoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC), cubosomes, model lipid membrane, Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), Cyclic voltammetry (CV)

1. Introduction

Nanocarriers (NCs) are used to improve drug solubility and sustainability, decrease the toxic side effects of drugs and deliver them across biological membranes into cells, addressing the carriers to the appropriate cells.^{1,2,3} The incorporation of an NC into the cell is controlled by several endocytosis processes that involve the enveloping and internalizing of the external NCs. Membrane fusion can be a successful strategy to perform the internalization step of an NC. In this process, after the contacting of two discrete lipid bilayers, fusion takes place, creating phospholipid domains and mixing internal components. Cubosomes have been proposed as excellent fusogenic NCs due to their unique properties⁴ i.e. thermodynamic stability, bioadhesion, and the ability to encapsulate hydrophilic, hydrophobic and amphiphilic substances. The potential for controlled release of the drug through functionalization, the delivery of a large drug load, and providing sustained release are some of the advantages connected with using cubosomes as drug carriers.⁵

Previous studies concerning phospholipid monolayer in the air-water interphase have demonstrated that the surface adsorption of cubosomes depends on the surface philicity as well as the internal structure of the cubosome material.⁶⁻⁹ However, these lipid membranes are single layers of a bilayer placed at the air –water interface. Another approach involves supported lipid bilayer (SLBs). Neutron reflectivity,^{10,11} quartz crystal microbalance (QCM)¹¹ and ellipsometry¹² have been used to investigate changes in lipid bilayers in the presence of cubosome material. Recently, Dyett et al. have observed the total fusion of lipid cubosomes NCs with lipid supported bilayers under flow conditions.¹³ Moreover, the fusion was facilitated in the cases of charged surfaces and also depended on the composition of the lipid layer.³ In a recent study, we used polarization modulation infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (PM-IRRAS) to demonstrate the effect of phytantriol-based cubosomes on the structure and lipid orientation of DMPC bilayers supported on Au (111) surfaces.¹⁴ We demonstrated that following the exposure to

cubosomes the acyl chains of the DMPC molecules in the bilayer adopt a more perpendicular orientation with respect to the surface. Moreover, the cone-shape structure of both molecules, DMPC and phytantriol, inverted in the case of phytantriol, allowed us to explain the tilt angle changes and lead us to propose the organization of the lipid membrane after exposure to cubosomes.

In the present study we investigate the effect of phytantriol-based cubosomes (PT- cubosomes) on the properties of DMPC bilayers supported on Au (111) electrode using electrochemical methods. A combination of Langmuir-Blodgett and Langmuir-Schaefer techniques was employed to prepare the supported lipid bilayers using the same approaches as reported in our recent paper¹⁴. Three electrochemical techniques, AC voltammetry, cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), as well as blocking assays using a redox probe were employed to evaluate the changes in the structure and electrical properties of the supported DMPC bilayers under the influence of cubosomes carriers. Exposure of a preformed bilayer to cubosome solution results in an increased resistance of the film reflecting spreading of cubosomes and formation of additional phytantriol/ Pluronic F-108 polymer layer on the top of the DMPC bilayer and improved barrier properties of the film. On the other hand, the formation of the bilayer in the presence of cubosomes in the solution results in the increased capacitance of the film reflecting penetration of the lipid layers by the phytantriol component of the cubosomes, and in result, larger porosity of the film.

Figure 1. (1) 1,2-dimyristoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC) – the bilayer forming compound, (2) phytantriol (PT) and (3) poly(ethylene glycol)-block-poly(propylene glycol)-block-poly(ethylene glycol), (Pluronic® F-108) – components of the cubosomes.

2. Experimental Section

2.1 Reagents and procedure for PT-based cubosomes preparation

Phytantriol (PT) derived cubosomes were prepared as described previously.¹⁴ Briefly, phytantriol was hydrated in the presence of Pluronic F-108 (PF-108) stabilizer, and then the suspension was homogenized using Sonics Vibra-Cell VCX 130 (Sonics & Materials Inc., USA) in three cycles of 20 minutes each. The PT content was 4.7 % w/w of the total dispersion weight. The ratio of PT to stabilizer was 3:1 (by weight). Cubosomal dispersion was equilibrated at room temperature for at least 24h. The structural parameters of cubosomes were assessed by small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) and cryoTEM. The diffraction patterns of the Pn3m PT-based cubosomes prepared in H₂O and the cryoTEM images of the lipid nanoparticles are presented in the Supplementary Information (Figures S1 and S2).

1,2-dimyristoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC), obtained from Avanti Polar Lipids, was dissolved in chloroform to obtain a final stock solution of 1 mg mL⁻¹. A 0.1 M NaF (Sigma Aldrich) or a 0.1M NaCl (Sigma Aldrich) solutions in ultra-pure water (Milli-Q, resistivity >

18.2 M Ω cm) was used as the supporting electrolyte. All reagents were used without any further purification.

For electrochemical measurements a polished 4.6 mm-diameter Au(111) disc purchased from MaTecK was employed as a working electrode.

Before each experiment, all the glassware was cleaned by standing it overnight in a potassium permanganate solution, washing it with a diluted mixture of H₂SO₄/H₂O₂ and finally meticulously rinsing it with Milli-Q water.

2.2 LB trough: pressure-area isotherms and sample preparation.

Surface pressure-area isotherms were recorded at the air-solution interface using a Langmuir trough (KSV NIMA) with KSV LB5000 software. The trough was equipped with two hydrophilic barriers and a Wilhelmy plate made with a filter paper (1 cm wide) which was replaced after every experiment. The experiments were performed at 22 ± 2 °C using as a subphase either pure Milli-Q water or a 0.15 mg L⁻¹ PT-based cubosomes solution prepared by diluting the stock solution.

DMPC bilayers were deposited on Au (111) electrodes using the two approaches described in our previous paper.¹⁴ In summary, in the first approach, the DMPC monolayer was formed on a pure water subphase and then transferred at the surface pressure of 30 mN m⁻¹ by Langmuir–Blodgett (LB) deposition. The electrode was dried for 1 h and the outer leaflet was transferred at a surface pressure of 30 mN m⁻¹ by the Langmuir–Schaefer (LS) method using 0.15 mg L⁻¹ solution of PT-based cubosomes as the subphase. In this approach, PT cubosomes were incorporated during the formation of the second monolayer and transferred in the outer leaflet of the bilayer on the gold electrode.

In the second approach, both DMPC monolayers were formed on a pure water subphase and transferred at 30 mN m⁻¹ onto the Au (111) electrode by the LB-LS method. Next, the DMPC

bilayer-modified electrode was exposed to a 0.15 mg L^{-1} solution of PT-based cubosomes for 2 hours. Finally, the drop over the electrode was carefully removed. Hence, in the latter approach PT-based cubosomes were placed in contact with the preformed Au (111)-supported DMPC bilayer.

2.3 Electrochemical measurements.

All electrochemical measurements were carried out with a CHI 75E multipurpose electrochemical system from CH Instruments equipped with a frequency response analyzer.

The polished 4.6 mm-diameter Au(111) disc (MaTecK) was employed as the working electrode. Before each experiment the single crystal face of the Au(111) electrode was flame-annealed and cooled in air. A flame-annealed platinum foil and Ag/AgCl electrode (saturated KCl), (CHI) were employed as the counter and reference electrodes, respectively. All potentials reported in this paper are referred to the Ag/AgCl electrode. Before each experiment, all glassware was cleaned by keeping it overnight in a potassium permanganate solution, then washed with a diluted mixture of $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ and finally meticulously rinsed with Milli-Q water. All the measurements were carried out at $22 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

AC voltammetry measurements were performed in a 0.1 M NaF solution between 0.3 and -0.9 V vs Ag/AgCl. Using a scan range of 5 mV s^{-1} a single sine AC perturbation with an amplitude of 10 mV was applied at a frequency of 20 Hz. The capacitance was calculated from the in-phase and out-phase components of the AC signal treating the electrochemical interface as a capacitor and resistor in series (RC circuit). The equivalent circuits fitting of the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy results was performed with ZSimpWin software (EG&G), which was developed based on Boukamp's model.

Prior to Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements in 0.1 M NaF, the stabilities of the coated electrodes were tested by scanning the potential in a small potential range around the pit of the AC voltammetry measurements. A well-formed and stable bilayer is

considered to be present when almost flat AC voltammetry curves are obtained and do not change in successive scans. For the EIS analysis, a step by step procedure was employed in which before each sample potential (E_{sample}) application, the Au(111)-supported bilayers were allowed to reorganize at -0.1 V vs Ag/AgCl ($E_{-0.1V}$). The cycles of $E_{-0.1V}/E_{\text{sample}}$ potential steps were repeated until a full impedance spectrum was recorded. At each sample potential pulses of frequency between 0.1 Hz and 10 kHz were applied.

Cyclic voltammetry experiments were performed in 0.1 M KCl solution, 1 mM with respect to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ at a scan rate of 50 mVs^{-1} . In the experiments with the redox couple in 0.1M KCl solution, the EIS measurements were carried out at a formal potential of the redox couple.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Compression isotherm results.

The incorporation of PT-based cubosomes into a DMPC monolayer formed at the air-water interface was followed by recording the surface pressure vs. area per molecule isotherms. PT cubosomes were dissolved in the aqueous subphase, over which DMPC monolayers were spread. Both components of the cubosomes – PT and the polymer were surface active and formed monolayers at the air water interface (Fig. 2a and b). The compression isotherms obtained for DMPC monolayers at the air-water interface, with and without cubosomes in the subphase, are shown in Figure 2c. The shift of the DMPC isotherm towards larger areas per molecule in the presence of cubosomes reflected the incorporation of the cubosome material into the monolayer.

Inset plots in Fig. 2 represent the compression modulus, C_s^{-1} as a function of the surface pressure. C_s^{-1} is described by equation (1):

$$C_s^{-1} = -A \frac{d\pi}{dA} \quad (1)$$

where π is the surface pressure of the monolayer and A is the area per molecule.

The increasing compressibility factor, C_s^{-1} , indicated that incorporation of the cubosomes material into the DMPC layer led to a more condensed mixed layer, however it was less condensed than that of PT alone.

Figure 2. Surface pressure-area per molecule isotherms of (a) PT, (b) pluronic F-108, (c) DMPC spread on pure aqueous subphase (black solid line) and subphases containing increasing concentration of cubosomes 0.05 (red), 0.10 (green), 0.15 (dark blue), 0.25 (light blue), 0.35 mg L^{-1} (magenta). Insert – compressibility factor vs. surface pressure for increasing concentration of cubosomes in the solution.

The DMPC monolayers, formed at the air-water interphase in the presence and absence of PT-based cubosomes in the subphase, were transferred onto Au(111) electrodes at 30 mN m^{-1} . At this surface pressure the incorporated cubosome material contained only the PT component because the Pluronic F-108 had already been expelled from the layer at lower surface pressures as shown in Figure 2b. The gold (111) electrode was covered a) with the DMPC bilayer, b) with DMPC bilayer in which PT-based cubosomes were incorporated from the subphase during the formation and transfer of the external leaflet of the bilayer or c) with the DMPC bilayer formed using pure water as the subphase, transferred onto gold and then exposed to 0.15 mg L^{-1} PT-based cubosomes solution for 2 hours. Previously we have demonstrated by PM-IRRAS measurements that the incorporation of PT-based cubosomes into DMPC bilayer led to a more close to perpendicular orientation of the DMPC molecules with respect to the Au(111) surface.¹⁴ In the present study, the electrical properties of these three types of bilayer-covered electrodes were compared using electrochemical methods.

3. 2 Electrochemical results in 0.1M NaF solutions

3.2.1 AC voltammetry measurements

AC voltammetry measurements were employed to characterize the effect of the PT-based cubosomes' incorporation into the DMPC supported bilayers on the Au(111) electrode as a function of the applied potential. The AC voltammetry plot of the DMPC supported bilayers, either in the presence or absence of PT-cubosomes, showed a minimum of the capacitive current in the potential range from -0.5 to 0.1 V vs. Ag/AgCl. The reproducible capacitance values of ca. $4\text{-}6 \text{ }\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ indicated that stable and densely packed bilayers were formed on the gold (111) electrode surface. However, the capacitance for the DMPC bilayer exposed to PT-based cubosomes solution for 2 hours is clearly smaller than that of the pure DMPC bilayer or that in which PT-based cubosomes were only incorporated during the formation and transfer of the second leaflet (Table S1). The decreased capacitance reflected a more densely packed layer when

the previously organized DMPC bilayer was exposed to PT-based cubosomes for 2h. At potential more negative than -0.5 V, the differential capacitance curves of all three DMPC-supported started to overlap and became similar to the curve corresponding to that of the bare gold electrode, indicating that the layer was desorbed from the electrode surface. The maximum of the capacitance at -0.7 V vs. Ag/AgCl confirmed the desorption of the DMPC supported bilayer from the gold (111) surface. At positive potentials, the three types of modified electrodes showed a maximum of capacitance at 0.2 V, corresponding to the reorientation of the film or the penetration of the anions from the supporting electrolyte as previously described in the literature.¹⁵ However, at potentials close to 0.1 V, the incorporation of PT-cubosomes into the DMPC bilayer clearly caused a decrease in the capacitance suggesting that either incorporation of PT-cubosomes reduced the penetration of anions or reduced the defect density of the DMPC bilayers at these potentials.¹⁶

Figure 3. AC voltammetry measurements of the gold electrode (1, - dashed dark line), supported DMPC bilayer (2, - solid green line), supported DMPC bilayer where PT cubosomes were incorporated during outer leaflet formation and transfer (3, - solid red line) and DMPC bilayer

deposited on Au(111) and subsequently exposed to 0.15 mg L^{-1} PT- cubosome solution for 2 hours (4, - solid blue line).

3.2.3 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements

More precise and quantitative information concerning the effects of the PT-cubosomes' incorporation into the DMPC bilayer on the Au (111) electrodes was obtained from EIS measurements. Figure 4 shows the total impedance and the corresponding phase angle of the supported DMPC bilayer in the presence and absence of PT-based cubosomes at potentials of 0 and -0.2 V. At both potentials the values of impedance were similar, however, the phase angle values were smaller at low frequencies when PT-based cubosomes were incorporated into the DMPC layer during the formation and transfer of the second leaflet. Qualitatively, this implies that PT-based cubosomes incorporated during the formation of the second leaflet lead to a more defective DMPC bilayer. Not unexpectedly, this effect was not seen when a preformed DMPC bilayer was subsequently exposed to PT-based cubosomes for 2 hours.

Figure 4. a-b) Total impedance and c-d) phase angles results obtained from the EIS measurements of electrodes covered with DMPC bilayer (green line), DMPC bilayer with PT cubosomes incorporated during formation of the second leaflet (red line) and preformed DMPC bilayer subsequently exposed to 0.15 mg L^{-1} PT-cubosomes solution for 2 hours (blue line). Values of the angular frequency (ω) are given in Hz.

In the next step, the impedance data at each potential were analyzed as a function of frequency employing the equivalent circuit to model the electrode interface as shown in Fig 5a.¹⁷ R_{ohm} is the resistance of the electrolyte solution while the Au(111)-supported lipid bilayer is represented by the constant phase element (CPE_m)(Fig. 5a). The impedance associated with the constant phase element is described by equation (2):

$$Z_{\text{CPE}} = \frac{1}{Q(j\omega)^{-\alpha}} \quad (2)$$

where Q - the frequency independent parameter is expressed in $\mu\text{F cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{\alpha-1}$ and α is the frequency dispersion ranging between 0 and 1. If $\alpha=1$, Z_{CPE} is frequency independent, becoming a pure capacitance. Values of α smaller than 1 are attributed to surface roughness or heterogeneities of the electrode surface.¹⁸

Fig 5 shows reasonable values of CPE_m , and α , obtained by fitting the ESI data to the equivalent circuit. Numerical values are collected in Tables S2. For the electrodes coated with a DMPC bilayer either exposed or not to the PT-cubosome solution, the numerical values α ranged from 0.96 down to 0.91 (Table S2) in the potentials from 0.1 to -0.5 V, indicating that well organized preformed DMPC bilayers remained uniform even upon exposure to cubosomes. The minimum values of CPE_m (Fig. 5a) were in good agreement with the values obtained from AC measurements (Fig. 3). The CPE_m values plotted in Figure 5b of a pure DMPC bilayer increase when PT-based cubosomes were incorporated during the formation and transfer of the second leaflet indicating that the resulting DMPC membrane became more defective. Interestingly, if a preformed DMPC bilayer was exposed to the PT cubosome solution for 2h the CPE_m values were smaller than those for a pure DMPC bilayer. The smaller CPE_m values can be explained by formation of an additional layer on top of the bilayer. In this approach it consists also of the polymer constituent, Pluronic F-108, from the cubosomes. The barrier properties of such bilayers were improved following contact with cubosomes.

Figure 5. a) Scheme of the equivalent circuit used for the EIS system. b) Variation in the constant phase element (CPE_m) of the supported DMPC bilayer (green circles), supported DMPC bilayer with PT cubosomes incorporated during formation of the second leaflet (red circles) and

preformed Au(111)-supported DMPC bilayer, subsequently exposed to 0.15 mg L⁻¹ PT-cubosomes solution for 2 hours (blue circles) in 0.1 M NaF electrolyte.

3.3 Cyclic voltammetry and impedance spectroscopy in solutions containing [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻

/[Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ system

The blocking properties of DMPC bilayers on Au(111) electrodes following contact with PT cubosomes can be shown better when the [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻/ [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ redox couple is present in the solution as the electrochemical probe. Figure 6a and 6b shows the CV and EIS results, respectively, for a bare Au(111) electrode (dashed black line), an electrode covered with the DMPC bilayer (green circles), an electrode covered with the DMPC bilayer where PT cubosomes were incorporated during the formation of the second monolayer of DMPC (red circles) and a supported preformed DMPC bilayer subsequently exposed to a 0.15 mg L⁻¹ cubosomes solution for 2 hours (blue circles). CV curves for a bare Au(111) electrode showed the reversible behavior of the soluble electrochemical probe. The DMPC bilayer covered electrode showed, as expected, good barrier properties towards the [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻/ [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ redox couple. The charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) was much smaller when the outer leaflet of the bilayer was formed in the presence of PT-based cubosomes in the subphase (Table 1). This confirmed that the PT-based cubosomes' presence during the formation of the external layer affected the organization of the bilayer, making it more porous. The voltammetric probe could access the electrode more easily and came closer to its surface by penetrating the film.

On the other hand, when the previously prepared DMPC bilayer was subsequently exposed for 2h to cubosomes, the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) was much larger. The splitting of the voltammetric peaks corresponding to the [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻/ [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ redox couple was much larger than expected for a reversible diffusion-controlled process, confirming the improved barrier properties of the lipid bilayer. This again showed that the additional layer formed by the constituents of the cubosomes was present over the bilayer film.

Figure 6. a) Cyclic voltammograms for 1mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ redox couple in 0.1 M KCl at 50 mVs^{-1} and b) Nyquist plots recorded at formal potential for the bare Au (111) electrode (dashed black line), covered by DMPC bilayer (green circles), covered by DMPC bilayer with PT cubosomes incorporated during the outer leaflet formation (red circles), and the Au(111) first covered with the DMPC bilayer, and subsequently exposed to a 0.15 mg L^{-1} PT- cubosome solution for 2 hours (blue circles). Solid dark lines are the theoretical curves obtained by fitting to the equivalent circuit shown in Fig. 6b.

Table 1. EIS results for Au (111) bare electrode and the three types of bilayer-modified electrodes. 0.1 M KCl solution containing 1mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$.

	R_{ct} ($\text{k}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$)	E_a (V vs Ag/AgCl)
Au (111) bare electrode	0.094 ± 0.17	0.12
DMPC	1.41 ± 0.21	0.27
DMPC/cubosomes ¹	0.63 ± 0.07	0.21
DMPC/cubosomes ²	2.03 ± 0.28	0.38

DMPC/cubosomes¹ refers to Au(111) electrode covered by DMPC bilayer with PT cubosomes incorporated during the outer leaflet formation and DMPC/cubosomes² refers to Au(111)

electrode first covered with the DMPC bilayer, and subsequently exposed to 0.15 mg L⁻¹ PT-cubosome solution for 2 hours.

4. Conclusions

We have employed compression isotherms, cyclic voltammetry, AC voltammetry and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy to investigate the effect of lipid nanoparticles, cubosomes often used as drug carriers, upon an Au(111) supported DMPC bilayer as the model lipid membrane. An increase in the area per molecule of the surface-pressure–area per molecule isotherms and changes in the compression modulus of the DMPC monolayers formed at the air-water interface proved the incorporation of cubosomal material into the lipid layer. The DMPC bilayers were deposited on Au(111) electrodes at 30mN m⁻¹ by a combination of Langmuir-Blodgett and Langmuir-Schaefer (LB-LS) techniques. PT-based cubosomes were introduced into the phospholipid layer either during the formation and transfer of the second leaflet by the Langmuir-Schaefer (LS) approach or by exposing a preformed DMPC bilayer to a solution of cubosomes for 2 h. The inclusion of the carrier in the model membrane under different experimental conditions is easily probed and the modifications induced in the lipid organization are inferred by quantitative analysis of the responses of different electrochemical techniques.

Incorporation of PT-based cubosomes during the transfer and formation of the second leaflet made the DMPC bilayer more porous, the membrane resistance decreased compared to that of the bilayer covered electrode without contact with cubosomes. The voltammetric probe could easily penetrate the film covering the electrode and came closer to its surface.

If the DMPC bilayer was first formed, and subsequently exposed to the solution of PT-based cubosomes, the resulting film had much larger resistance and increased barrier properties compared with a DMPC bilayer not exposed to cubosomes, showing that an additional layer was formed on top of the lipid bilayer. Probably it contained PT as well as the polymer which was the second component of the cubosomes. The capacitance decreased while the resistance of the layer

was increased. The effect of cubosomes on the lipid membrane is, therefore, shown to depend on the way of preparing the bilayer. When it is formed in the presence of cubosomes, a highly porous layer is formed: The CPEm value is large pointing to a defective, porous film. Facilitated incorporation of the cubosome phytantriol into the lipid matrix leads to the enhancement of the porosity of the lipid membrane compared to that of pure DMPC layer, and the decrease of the film resistance is observed. On the other hand, when a preformed well-organized bilayer is exposed to the cubosome solution the high resistance reflects formation of an additional layer of cubosomal components forming additional layered structure on the top of the lipid bilayer. The PT component is incorporated preferably in the porous DMPC bilayer while hydrophilic and oxygen rich Pluronic F-108 prefers to remain on the top of the lipid layer in contact with water. This “extra” layer of Pluronic F-108 is the main cause of the high resistance and increased barrier properties of the film observed when a redox probe is added to the solution. Understanding of this behavior is important in view of the application of the studied cubosomes as nanocarriers delivering the drugs into the cells.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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